

Effect of buckwheat rotation with rice on total productivity in southern Ukraine

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Results from several experiment stations in Poltava, Sumy, and other areas in the Ukraine have shown that buckwheat is a good rotation crop. Productivity of winter wheat and rye after buckwheat is higher than after stubble crops (wheat, barley, oats) and silage corn. In some years, buckwheat, as a fertility-building crop, does not have the same effect as pea (Yefimenko and Barabash 1986). Its high efficiency as a rotation crop is confirmed by farmers working under different soil and climatic regions of the Ukraine.

Studies done by the Ukrainian Institute of Microbiology revealed the presence of nitrogen-fixing *Azospirillum brasilense* 18-2 in buckwheat root rhizosphere (Lokhova 1997). This is probably how the buckwheat root system improves soil fertility for the succeeding crops.

Buckwheat adds much fresh organic matter to the soil: the amount of stubble after buckwheat in the soil of the Ukrainian Experimental Station rice field was 26.4 t ha⁻¹ vs 24.3 t ha⁻¹ for alfalfa-grass sod. Repnikov (1991) found that grain yield of rice increased after buckwheat (4.7 t ha⁻¹) in contrast with rice after rice (2.2 t ha⁻¹).

Populidi (1976) reported that rice after buckwheat on a 60-ha rice farm in Romanovsky of the Rostov region (Russia) yielded 3.3 t ha⁻¹ and a 29-ha area 2.5 t ha⁻¹ under black fallow (unsown during vegetative period, weed-free) conditions.

The buckwheat trials were carried out under rice crop rotation conditions in Kherson District. The area is in the south steppe zone and is characterized by arid conditions with high temperature averaging 33.5 °C and scanty and unsteady air moisture. Mean daily air temperature during July-August is 23–24 °C; maximum air temperature reaches 38–40 °C, while soil surface temperature is 60–61 °C. Average annual rainfall is 360 mm. The average

windspeed is about 4 m s⁻¹, whereas maximum windspeed is 20 m s⁻¹. Annual evaporation for the region is about 900–1,000 mm. The longest of sunshine recorded is 15 h and 50 min. Climatic conditions in southern Ukraine allow two crops per year during the warm period.

The topsoil of the experimental site is meadow-chestnut (a semihydromorphic soil with clay feature), compressed, with a pH of 7.6, and a humus content of 2.1 in a surface soil of 20-cm depth. Sowing time for dry-seeded rice is early May; sowing time for the intercrop buckwheat is the first half of July. The rice cultivar used was Krasnodarsky 424, an Italian variety with 130-d duration, whereas the buckwheat cultivar used was Kosmeya with a 74-d duration. Rice was sown where buckwheat had been previously grown. The site under black fallow was used as a control in the same field.

Buckwheat was found to be better for rice than black fallow (Table 1). The average yield of intercropped buckwheat in 8-y field experiments under various pro-

duction situations was 1.6 t ha⁻¹. Buckwheat intercropped with rice can increase the harvest of both buckwheat and rice from irrigated lands.

We estimated the economic efficiency of intercropped buckwheat in a rice system. Table 2 gives comparative data for buckwheat and various crops.

The grain production cost of intercropped buckwheat was US\$199 ha⁻¹, with a net income of \$237 (based on an exchange rate of US\$1 = 5.2109 *grivnya* in Jan 2000). Thus, production cost was \$133 t⁻¹ and profitability was 119%. As a whole, total net incomes from double cropping are as follows: annual grass for green fodder + buckwheat = \$318; spring barley + buckwheat = \$394; and winter wheat + buckwheat = \$538.

Productivity of rice can be greatly improved by intercropping buckwheat with rice. This will allow more grain production from irrigated areas and increase the profitability of rice-based cropping systems.

Table 1. Effect of buckwheat as a pre-ribe crop on rice productivity.

Background	Rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Mean	Yield increment	
	1988	1989	1990		t ha ⁻¹	%
Fallow land (control)	7.9	5.7	7.1	6.9	–	–
Buckwheat	9.2	6.6	8.9	8.2	1.3	19
LSD (5%)				0.98		

Table 2. Economic performance of some crops in rice fields.

Item	Spring barley	Winter wheat	Annual grass green fodder	Buckwheat
Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	3.4	4.5	13.4	1.5
Value of gross product (US\$)	377	605	270	436
Production cost for 1 ha ⁻¹ (US\$)	220	308	189	199
Net income from 1 ha ⁻¹ (US\$)	157	301	81	237
Grain cost t ⁻¹ (US\$)	65	68	14	133
Profitability (%)	71.4	97.7	42.7	119.1

References

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Effects of salt and osmotic stress on free polyamine accumulation in moderately salt-resistant rice cultivar Aiwu

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Polyamines (putrescine, sermidine, and spermine) are ubiquitous and positively charged compounds involved in the control of plant growth and development and in the response to several biotic and abiotic stresses. Data on polyamine accumulation in salt-stressed rice are contradictory and generally deal with exposure of several days to NaCl only. Our aim was to determine whether the ionic or osmotic component of salt stress is involved in the initial steps of polyamine accumulation in rice.

Twenty-five-day-old plants of cultivar Aiwu maintained on nutrient solution (Yoshida et al 1976) in a phytotron (light intensity: 300 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, 12 h d^{-1} , 70% relative humidity, and 30/25 °C day/night temperatures) were exposed to isoosmotic concentrations of NaCl or KCl (50 and 100 mM) or PEG (polyethylene glycol 6000; 16% and 26%). These stressing agents induced a decrease in osmotic potential of nutrient solution corresponding to -0.12 and -0.25 MPa for the two stress intensities, respectively. Stress imposition corre-

sponded to the beginning of the light period and plants were collected after 3 and 12 h of exposure. Osmotic potential (ψ_s) and ion content were quantified separately on roots and shoots using a vapor pressure osmometer (Wescor) and an inductively coupled argon plasma emission spectrophotometer according to Lutts et al (1999). Endogenous free polyamine was quantified by a Shimadzu RF-10Axl fluorimeter after separation by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) according to Aziz et al (1999).

Dry weight percentages (DW; in %), osmotic potential ψ_s (in MPa), Na^+ and K^+ concentrations (in mmol g^{-1} DW) in roots and shoots of plants exposed for 3 or 12 h to isoosmotic concentrations of NaCl or KCl (50 or 100 mM) or PEG (16% or 26%). The two stress intensities correspond to an induced decrease in osmotic potential of nutrient solution of -0.12 and -0.25 MPa, respectively. Values are means of eight replicates per treatment: for a given parameter, means of the same line followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$, according to the method of Duncan using the MSTAT-C system (Michigan State University).

		-0.12 MPa				-0.25 MPa		
		Control	50 mM NaCl	50 mM KCl	16% PEG	100 mM NaCl	100 mM KCl	26% PEG
Roots	3 h							
	DW	14.80 a	19.30 b	16.60 a	21.80 b	29.60 c	14.50 a	23.50 b
	ψ_s	-0.32 a	-0.57 b	-0.58 b	-0.32 a	-0.62 b	-0.73 c	-0.35 a
	Na^+	0.07 a	0.37 b	0.12 a	0.06 a	0.63 c	0.07 a	0.08 a
	K^+	0.84 a	0.93 a	1.31 b	0.76 a	0.86 a	1.85 c	0.69 a
	12 h							
	DW	13.90 a	18.10 b	11.40 a	20.50 b	22.10 b	11.70 a	22.80 b
	ψ_s	-0.31 a	-0.53 b	-0.37 a	-0.25 a	-0.45 b	-0.35 a	-0.37 a
Na^+	0.08 a	0.82 b	0.08 a	0.11 a	0.75 b	0.13 a	0.09 a	
K^+	0.62 a	0.96 b	1.67 c	0.57 a	1.09 b	3.02 c	0.67 b	
Shoots	3 h							
	DW	17.30 a	18.00 a	17.40 a	19.80 a	19.20 a	19.50 a	21.80 b
	ψ_s	-1.02 a	-1.16 a	-1.12 a	-1.34 b	-1.05 a	-1.17 a	-1.31 b
	Na^+	0.03 a	0.13 b	0.05 a	0.03 a	0.17 c	0.02 a	0.03 a
	K^+	1.24 a	1.32 a	1.46 b	1.09 a	1.15 a	1.43 b	0.98 a
	12 h							
	DW	16.30 a	16.60 a	18.30 a	24.20 b	20.10 a	20.40 a	25.30 b
	ψ_s	-1.64 a	-1.66 a	-1.63 a	-2.08 b	-1.57 a	-1.50 a	-2.46 c
Na^+	0.05 a	0.16 b	0.03 a	0.04 a	0.19 b	0.04 a	0.03 a	
K^+	1.13 a	1.15 a	1.29 b	0.91 a	1.19 a	1.61 c	0.97 a	